

Etiology of Pancytopenia in Pediatric Population Attending in R.I.M.S, RanchiShaor Nazish¹, M A Ansari², Alok Kumar³^{1,3}Tutor, Department of Pathology, Shahid Nirmal Mahato Medical College and Hospital, Dhanbad India²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology RIMS, Ranchi

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Alok Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Pancytopenia is an important clinico- hematological entity worldwide but with different patterns in clinical presentation. Alterations in peripheral blood counts resulting in Pancytopenia are commonly encountered in pediatric practice and etiology in these patients are quite varied.**Objective:** To find out and analyze the various causes of pancytopenia in Pediatric population attending in R.I.M.S, Ranchi.**Methods:** The present study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, and Ranchi. The permission to conduct this study was obtained from the central research committee of R.I.M.S and the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC).**Results:** Age & sex distribution of patients with pancytopenia in this study was consistent with the findings in other studies. Megaloblastic anemia was the commonest cause of pancytopenia in the present study. 2nd most common cause was Hypoplastic anemia A significant percentage of them had a history of intake of bone marrow suppressant drugs, which could be avoided easily. Other causes were hypersplenism, Mixed nutritional deficiency anemia, Acute leukaemia and among them, megaloblastic anemia & mixed nutritional deficiency anemia are easily preventable. Rare causes like Gaucher's disease have also been identified in our study.**Conclusions:** Bone marrow study of patients with pancytopenia usually helps in identification of the etiology. It is very important to diagnose the cause of pancytopenia early in the disease process, so that adequate intervention could be done on time for the patient.**Keywords:** Bone Marrow Study, Pancytopenia, Hypersplenism, Acute Leukaemia, Megaloblastic Anemia.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Pancytopenia is not a disease entity but a triad of findings that may result from a number of disease processes primarily or secondarily involving the bone marrow. The presenting symptoms are usually attributable to the anemia or thrombocytopenia and rarely leucopenia which in later stages is responsible for the downhill course. Various factors encompassing geographic distribution and genetic disturbances may cause variations in the incidence of disorders causing pancytopenia. [1,2,3]. Underlying pathology determines the management and prognosis of the patients [4].

A wide variety of disorders can cause pancytopenia, although the frequency with which each condition is associated with pancytopenia differs considerably. The underlying mechanisms are decrease in hematopoietic stem cell production, marrow replacement by abnormal cells, suppression of marrow growth, ineffective hematopoiesis and cell death, defective cell formation which are removed from the circulation, antibody mediated sequestra-

tion and destruction of cells and trapping of cells in hypertrophied and overactive reticulo-endothelial system. [5,16]. Pancytopenia can result from damage to the bone marrow evidenced by low reticulocyte count or increased destruction of preformed blood cells peripherally with increased reticulocyte count [7]

The etiology of pancytopenia varies widely in children, ranging from transient marrow suppression by virus to marrow infiltration by life-threatening malignancy. These may also be caused iatrogenically, secondary to certain drugs, chemotherapy or radiotherapy for malignancies. The bone marrow picture may vary depending on the etiology, from normocellular with non-specific changes to hypercellular being replaced completely by malignant cells. According to etiology, degree and duration of the impairment, clinically these can lead to fever, pallor, infection, or serious illness and death. Knowing the exact etiology is important for specific treatment and prognosis. Primary or genetic

causes include Fanconi anemia, dyskeratosis congenita, Swachman's diamond syndrome and amegakaryocytic thrombocytopenia.[8] Acquired cases can be idiopathic or secondary to exposure to radiation, drugs and chemicals (chemotherapy chloramphenicol, sulfa group, anti-epileptics etc) , viral infections (cyto megalovirus, Epstein barr, hepatitis B or C , HIV etc), auto immune PNH and marrow replacement disorders (leukemia , myelodysplasia) [9]

Megaloblastic anemia and infections such as enteric fever, malaria, kalazar and bacterial infections can be common cause of pancytopenia in developing countries. [8] Nutritional megaloblastic anemia is also one of the leading causes of pancytopenia in younger children. [9] Bone marrow profile is useful in the diagnosis of both hematological and non-hematological disorders. For Bone marrow interpretation, the history, clinical feature, bone marrow aspiration, peripheral blood smear, serum Iron, serum ferritin, serum vit B12 and serum folic acid are required Hence this study was conducted to find out and analyze the various causes of pancytopenia in Pediatric population attending in R.I.M.S, Ranchi

Materials and Methods:

This Prospective study was conducted among pediatric patients of age group 2 months to 18 years with pancytopenia referred to Department of Pathology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi for one year period (2017 to 2018) depending upon inclusions and exclusions criteria. The permission to conduct this study was obtained from the central research committee of R.I.M.S and the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC).The study period is from July 2017 to June 2018.

Sample size: A minimum of 100 pediatric patients suspected for pancytopenia was included in the study.

Selection of Cases: Diagnosis of Pancytopenia Is Based on Hb < 10 gm/dl ANC < 1.5×10^9 /L Platelet count < 1,00,000/cumm

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Pediatric patients of age 2 months to 18 years were included.
2. Pediatric patients (2 months to 18years) fulfilling the criteria for pancytopenia was included

Exclusion Criteria

1. Recent or ongoing infection , systemic illness
2. Patients with history receiving cancer chemotherapy, radiotherapy, recent bloodtransfusion, and treatment of anemia
3. Subjects not willing to give consent

Methodology: After taking particulars (Name, age,

sex, address) of the patients, a detailed clinical history including presenting complaints, dietary history and drug history are taken. After that general physical and systemic examination are done with special reference to pallor, status of lymph node, liver & spleen.

Then 2 ml of EDTA (ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid) anticoagulated peripheral venous blood is collected and processed through SYSMEX-XT2000i automated hematology analyser.

Peripheral blood smear is evaluated under the following headings: Red blood cell White blood cell Platelet Haemoparasite

Bone marrow aspiration study

Sites of bone marrow aspiration: Anterior iliac crest, posterior iliac crest & Tibia.

Commonly employed needles for marrow aspiration needles are Salah bone marrow aspiration needle.

Method of aspiration:

1. The patient was made to lie in the left lateral position and hip and knee were flexed.
2. Skin covering the site was cleaned with betadine, spirit and betadine under aseptic precautions.
3. 3-5 ml of 2% xylocaine was injected into the skin overlying the aspiration site and also into the periosteum.
4. Salah needle along with its stylet and guard (adjusted according to the thickness of the subcutaneous tissue) was introduced through the skin into the bone and rotated in clockwise and anticlockwise directions. Needle was pushed through the cortex into the medullary bone ascertained by sudden disappearance of resistance against the needle.
5. The stylet was withdrawn and a 10 ml syringe was attached to the needle. Negative suction was applied to draw not more than 0.2 of marrow into the syringe.
6. Needle and syringe together were withdrawn and marrow was poured onto the slides placed at an angle of 30° so that blood present in marrow could be drained off.
7. Smears of bone marrow were made quickly to avoid clotting and stained with Leishman's stain. Good marrow smears contain marrow particles as well as trail of particles.

Differential Count on The Bone Marrow: At least 500 nucleated marrow cells under oil immersion magnification are counted.

Biochemical examination: Peripheral venous blood is collected in plain tube and sent to biochemistry department for estimation of serum ferritin, vitamin B12 & folic acid level.

Flow Cytometry

Instrument-

1. BD biosciences 6 color Flow Cytometer
2. Centrifuge
3. Vortex mixer

Statistical Analysis: All the relevant data so collected are entered in the master chart and analysed using appropriate statistical procedure and software.

Statistical analysis of the data is done using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Software, version 23.0 (IBM). The student's T test is used to compare mean values of quantitative variables. Qualitative variables are analysed by chi square test. Statistical significance will be consid-

ered for p values less than 0.05. Values are presented as charts, bar diagrams etc. Results are discussed and correlated with the analysed literature and conclusion is drawn keeping in mind about the limitation of the study.

Results

In our study, a total of 100 cases of Pediatric patients with pancytopenia were studied. Out of 100 cases, 53 patients were male and 47 were female. The mean age of the study population was 12±5.4.

Among it, mean age of males was 12±5.76 and mean age of females was 12±5. Most of the study population was between in 12 - 18 years both in males and females. It was found that there is no significant statistical difference between the mean age of males and females.

Table 1: Demographic Profile Of Study Population

Variables	Case(n)	Male	Female	P value
Study population	100	54	46	
Mean age	12.0±5.4	12±5.7	12±5	
0.2-1 yr	08	07	01	NS
>1-5 yr	14	08	06	
>5-12 yr	26	10	16	
>12 yr	52	29	23	

Most of the cases (52%) were in the age group of 12-18 years followed by 26% cases were in the age group 5-12 years.

Least number of cases 08% was in the age group of less than 1 year. It was found that male are more commonly affected than females in all age groups except 5-12 years groups, there is no significant

statistical difference between the age groups of cases. Here the bar diagram shows that a total of 55 cases were non-vegetarian and 45 cases were vegetarian. Among the non-vegetarians, 35 were males and 20 were female cases.

Among the 45 vegetarian cases, 26 cases were males and 19 cases were females.

Figure 1: vertical bar diagram showing gender wise distribution of dietary history

Figure 2: Column Graph Showing Gender Wise Distribution of Bone Marrow Suppressant History

Here it is shown that only 07 cases (out of 100) were found to have a history of intake of bone marrow suppressant drug. Among them 4 cases were males and 3 cases were females. The drugs were anti-epileptics, anti malarials, antibiotics (chloramphenicol, cephalosporin) and NSAIDs.

Here it is shown that, the most common presenting chief complaint was Fever, which was present in 45% of cases. The second most common was Malaise (present in 23% of cases), followed by abdominal distension (17% of cases). The other chief

complaints were bleeding (8%), and rashes (7%).

Here the column graph shows that, the most common diagnosis among 100 patients of pancytopenia was Megaloblastic anaemia (38%), followed by Aplastic anaemia (30%).

The next common diagnosis was Erythroid hyperplasia (11%), followed by mixed nutritional anaemia (07%), & acute leukaemia (5%).

The other 3 diagnosis were Hypersplenism (2%), Gaucher’s disease (2%) and Normal study (5%).

Table 2: Gender Wise Distribution of Mean Haemoglobin, Mean Total Leukocyte Count and Mean Platelet Count

Variables	Mean	Case (n=100)	Male	Female	P Value
Hb		5.66±1.98	5.7±1.8	5.6±2.1	NS
Mean TLC		2921±925	2812±864	3050±987	NS
Mean Platelet		55907±26581	58148±26686	53276±26506	NS

The mean haemoglobin of the study population was 5.66±1.98gm/dl. The mean total leukocyte count was 2921±925/cu.mm. The mean platelet count of the study population was 55907±26581 /cu.mm.

It was found that there is no significant statistical difference between mean haemoglobin, mean total leukocyte count and mean platelet count.

Figure 3: Vertical Bar Diagram Showing Gender Wise Distribution Of Bone Marrow Cellularity

Here it shows that out of 100 cases, 51 cases were found to have with bone marrow hyper cellularity and 10 been mild hypercellular on bone marrow aspiration. Among hypercellular, 29 patients were males and 22 were female. In 30 cases bone marrow

aspiration was hypocellular. Among them, 16 cases were males and 14 cases were females. And 9 cases were normocellular on aspiration. It was found that gender wise distribution of bone marrow cellularity was not statistically significant.

Figure 4: Column Graph Showing Gender Wise Distribution Of Bone Marrow Erythropoiesis

It was found in bone marrow aspiration that bone marrow erythropoiesis was hyperplastic & megaloblastic in 38 case, of them 25 patients were male and 13 patients were female. The next common finding of depressed marrow was seen in 30 cases. Of them 16 were male and 14 were female. The

other marrow findings were normoblastic normoplastic and hyperplastic with few micronormoblast in 8 cases each. The rest findings were normoblastic hypoplastic, micronormoblastic hyperplastic and with Gaucher cells in 2 cases each.

Figure 5: Column Graph Showing Gender Wise Distribution of Bone Marrow Leukopoiesis

In bone marrow aspiration, leucopoiesis was found to be depressed in 30 patients, of them 16 cases were males. In 22 cases leucopoiesis was found to be normal. Giant metamyelocyte were found in 43 cases & blasts were found in only 5 cases. It was found that there is no significant statistical difference of gender wise distribution of these variables.

Figure 6: Column Graph Showing Gender Wise Distribution of Bone Marrow Megakaryopoiesis

Bone marrow aspiration showed that, megakaryopoiesis was depressed in 35 patients. Of them, 17 cases were males & 18 cases were female. Megakaryopoiesis was normal in 65 patients, out of which 37 cases were males, and there was no significant statistical difference between males and females.

Figure 7: Column Graph Showing Gender Wise Distribution of Final Impression

Here the column graph shows that, out of 38(38%) patients diagnosed as Megaloblastic anaemia 25(65.8%) cases were males and 13 (34.2%) cases were females. Aplastic anemia is found in 30 cases. Out of 30(30%) patients 16(53%) cases were males and 14(47%) cases were females. Among 2(2%) cases of hypersplenism, 50% were male and 50% were females. In 7(7%) cases of mixed nutritional anemia, 2 (28.5%) were male and 5(71.5%) were females. Among 5(5%) cases of Acute leukemia 1(20%) was male and 4(80%) were females. There were 11(11%) cases of Erythroid hyperplasia. 6(54.5%) were males and 5(45.4%) were females. And the rest 5 (5%) cases were normal study cases. Among them 2(40%) were males and 3(60%) were females. It was found that there is no significant statistical difference of final impression in male and female patients.

Discussion

Pancytopenia is a feature of many transient illnesses or serious life-threatening diseases. The frequency of pattern of diseases causing them varies in different population groups and this has been attributed to differences in methodology and stringency of diagnostic criteria, geographic area, period of observation, genetic differences, nutritional status, prevalence of infections and varying exposure to myelotoxic drugs among others. The published studies on pancytopenia have also been limited by the referral nature of patient population. Jha et al. from Nepal studied the causes of pancytopenia

in 148 patients. The commonest etiology of pancytopenia in their study was hypoplastic bone marrow seen in 43 cases (29%), followed by megaloblastic anemia in 35 cases (23.6%) and hematological malignancy in 32 cases (21.6%). In children, hypoplastic bone marrow (38.1%) and in adults megaloblastic anemia (30.2%) was the commonest etiology reported by them. A study from Pakistan found megaloblastic anemia as the most prevalent diagnosis and the major cause of bicytopenia and pancytopenia in the bone marrow aspirates performed in their pediatric unit. [5]

In children, Bhatnagar et al., [8] who retrospectively analyzed 109 pediatric patients presenting with pancytopenia, found megaloblastic anemia as the single most common etiological factor causing pancytopenia in 28.4% children, followed by acute leukemia and infections in 21% patients each, and aplastic anemia in 20% cases. Tilak et al (1999). [10] And Bhatnagar et al (2005) [8] from India also showed Megaloblastic Anemia as the most common cause of Pancytopenia in children.

In the present study out of 100 patients, 54 were male patients, making the male female ratio 1.7:1. In various studies conducted on pancytopenia, male preponderance was noted like male female ratio was 1.3:1 by Khodke et al [11], and 1.79:1 by Bhatnagar et al. [8] The most common presenting chief complaint was Fever, which was present in 45% of cases. The second most common was Malaise (present in 23% of cases), followed by ab-

dominal distension (17% of cases). The other chief complaints were bleeding (8%), and rashes (7%). Naseem et al, Rathod et al in their studies also found Fever as the most common symptom. In the study conducted by Bhatnagar et al [8] bleeding was the most common symptom.

In the present study 100% of the study population presented with pallor, in addition 16% had pallor with splenomegaly, 7% had hepatosplenomegaly & 10% had hepatosplenomegaly in addition to pallor and 2% had lymphadenopathy. Naseem et al in their studies found Pallor (59%) as the most common sign followed by hepatomegaly in 51% and splenomegaly in 37%.

Megaloblastic anemia: This was the most common cause (38%) of pancytopenia in our study. Similar incidences were observed by Bhatnagr et al. [8] & Savage et al., who reported the incidence of megaloblastic anemia to be 28% & 35% respectively in their studies. In studies conducted by. Khodke et al. [11], and Tilak et al [10], they found very high incidence of megaloblastic anemia (72.9% & 43.22% and 68% respectively), making it the most common cause of pancytopenia in their studies. The most common age group having megaloblastic anemia was 12- 18 years (52%) in our study. The male female ratio for megaloblastic anemia was 1.9:1. It was more common (95.5%) in vegetarian patients. All patients had macrocytic normochromic RBCs with hyper segmented neutrophil in PBS.

Hypoplastic/Aplastic anemia: In the present study, aplastic anemia was the 2nd most common cause (30%) of pancytopenia, which correlated with the corresponding figures in study done by Bhatnagr et al[8], Khunger et al, Khodke et al[11],. and Tilak et al[10],

Erythroid Hyperplasia: In the present study, Erythroid hyperplasia was the 3rd most common finding (11%) of pancytopenia. Khodke et al in their study also found Erythroid hyperplasia (14%) as the 3rd most common finding of Pancytopenia along with Kalazar. However Jha et al in his study found Erthroid hypeplasia (23.8%) as the 2nd most common finding of Pancytopenia

Mixed Nutritional Anemia: Mixed nutritional anemia (i.e. combination of iron deficiency and megaloblastic anemia in varying proportions, the megaloblastic change being partially masked by super-added iron deficiency) was found in 07% of study population in our study. 71.4% of them had dimorphic RBCs in PBS. Bone marrow aspiration in them was mildly hypercellular with erythroid hyperplasia with both micronormoblastic and occasional megaloblastoid maturation. These patients had low serum ferritin level & slightly lower Vitamin B12 in their biochemical estimation.

Acute Leukemia: Acute leukaemia was found in

5% patients in our study, compared to 2.0% reported by Khodke et al [11], 26.6%. 4 cases (80%) were of B cell leukemia and 1(20%) case was of T cell leukemia. 4 of them were female patients in our study. 2 of them were in the age group 1–5 years & the other 2 in the age group of 12 –181 in the age group of 5-12years. 3 cases presented with fever and rest of the 2 patients presented with abdominal distension. 60% of acute leukemia had hepatomegaly and 40% had lymphadenopathy in addition to hepatosplenogaly and pallor. PBS showed occasional three or four blast cells along with pancytopenia. Bone marrow aspiration revealed hypercellular bone marrow with predominance of blasts (more than 80%).

Hypersplenism: In this study only 2 (2%) cases presented with hypersplenism. Rathod et al in their study also found only 2.5% case of hypersplenism. While the studies conducted by Jha et al found 6.25% of hypersplenism cases.50% of patients with hypersplenism presented with abdominal distension .Male to female ratio was 1:1. 50% of the patient presented with abdominal distension. All the patients had pallor with enlarged palpable spleen at presentation. In PBS all the patients of hypersplenism had normocytic normochromic RBCs. Bone marrow aspiration was mildly hypercellular to normocellular with normoblastic and hyperplastic erythropoiesis. Leukopoiesis and megakaryopoiesis were within normal limits.

Conclusion

Age & sex distribution of patients with pancytopenia in this study was consistent with the findings in other studies. Megaloblastic anemia was the commonest cause of pancytopenia in the present study. 2nd most common cause was Hpoplastic anemia A significant percentage of them had a history of intake of bone marrow suppressant drugs, which could be avoided easily. Other causes were hypersplenism, Mixed nutritional deficiency anemia, Acute leukaemia and .Among them, megaloblastic anemia & mixed nutritional deficiency anemia are easily preventable. A rare cause like Gaucher's disease has also been identified in our study.

The limitation of the study includes a small sample size. Studies with larger sample size with long follow up periods can further establish the etiological patterns and progression of pancytopenia in pediatric population.

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